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Audit Quality and Financial Performance of Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Audit quality refers to the thoroughness, reliability, and accuracy of an audit process, which determines the likelihood of an auditor detecting and reporting material misstatements in financial statements or non-compliance with standards. High audit quality results in a high level of confidence that financial reports are accurate and free from errors or fraud, establishing trust for users. The study examined the effect of audit quality on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Specifically, the study analyzed the effect of audit fee, audit size and auditor committee on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study is anchored on the agency theory. The study adopted ex-post facto research design. Secondary data was collected from financial statements of the selected manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The analysis was done using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, fixed and random effect test and regression analysis for the test of hypotheses. The result of the study indicate that audit fee and audit size has significant effect on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria while and auditor committee has no significant effect on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study concludes that audit quality has positive and significant effect on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study recommends that manufacturing firms should not be in a hurry to assign more than one responsibility to each of the auditor committee since it has significant effect on return on asset.

Keywords: Audit Quality, Financial Performance, Manufacturing Firms, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Audit quality is critical in accounting and finance, reflecting the degree to which an audit meets professional standards and enhances the reliability of financial statements. DeAngelo (1981) defines audit quality as the market-assessed joint probability that an auditor will both (a) discover a breach in the client's accounting system and (b) report the breach. This emphasizes the auditor's competence and independence. Deden, Giawan, and Zamri (2019) argued that auditing services play a crucial role in moderating the conflict between business owners and management interests, as projected in agency theory. Ogbeifun and Olorunsola (2020) further explained that the quality of financial reporting hinges on the role of external audits in supporting the financial reporting standards of quoted companies. Investment communities and other stakeholders, particularly investors in insurance firms, rely on credible reports from independent audit services to foster business activities and accurately measure financial performance. Similarly, Ado, Rashid, Mustapha, and Ademola (2020) emphasized that a quality audit forms the foundation for confidence in the integrity and credibility of financial reports, highlighting it as one of the most critical issues in audit practice today.

Financial reports audited by reputable independent firms uphold market confidence more than those audited by inexperienced firms. Audits of financial statements and related assurance services act as monitoring mechanisms that help reduce information asymmetry, prevent fraudulent practices, correct errors, and identify material misstatements. They also safeguard assets and evaluate the effectiveness of internal control systems by providing reasonable assurance that financial statements are free from material misstatement. Firms, public or private, are established for specific objectives. Among these objectives, profit-making is predominant, especially for private firms, who must make enough revenue to cover costs, or at least equals costs, to continue operations. Therefore, the need to increase revenue and reduce costs in order to earn profit is at the heart of many firms, especially to remain competitive in the industry. Firms' performances may be financial or otherwise. Examples of non-financial performance indices are customer satisfaction, employee motivation, high market share, among others, while financial performance may be measured as profit after tax, profit before tax, return on assets, return on equity, positive and sustainable operating cashflow, etc. The financial statement is typically prepared, as stewardship report by management on how resources of the firm were used. It is a medium through which the financial health of the firm is reported and evaluated by members (shareholders). In order to get assurance on the credibility of the financial statements, shareholders engage auditors to assist in examining such financial statements and give a report on their truthfulness and fairness.

Statement of the Problem

The financial crises and collapse of a number of industries which prompted accounting regulators to examine carefully, as never before, the reporting practices and accounting standards have helped in generating pressures that motivated changes in the audit quality reporting in the financial statements in the country. The financial scandals have shown the incapacity of these concepts (auditor's competence and independence) to guarantee audit quality on their own. These have created a revolution in the design and evaluation of the audit quality which needs total reinforcement in order to solve this problem. The need for high quality external audit has become a global concern following corporate scandals involving Enron; World Com; Global Crossing; Cendant; Sunbeam (United States); BCCI; Independent Insurance; Equitable Life; Maxwell (United Kingdom); Metallgesellschaft (Germany); Lever Brothers; African Petroleum; Cadbury; Savanna Bank; Wewa Bank and Intercontinental Bank (Nigeria). The persistent firms' failures all over the world have raised some fundamental issues on the quality of audit, independence of the external auditors, among others. The poor audit reports from companies have made attraction of quality and sustainable foreign investments in Nigeria elusive. Studies have shown that the confidence of users of financial statements has been increasingly destroyed by the poor quality of audit reports presented in the financial statements issued in Nigeria (Enekwe, Onyekwelu, Nwoha & Okwo, 2016). In the light of the above, the major problem of this study is to determine the effect of audit quality on financial performance of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Audit Quality

Audit quality is critical in accounting and finance, reflecting the degree to which an audit meets professional standards and enhances the reliability of financial statements. DeAngelo (1981) defines audit quality as the market-assessed joint probability that an auditor will both (a) discover a breach in the client's accounting system and (b) report the breach. This emphasizes the auditor's competence and independence. Francis (2004) expands on DeAngelo's definition, proposing that audit quality involves technical capabilities and professional skepticism. According to Francis, audit quality is determined by the auditor's adherence to relevant standards, ensuring that financial statements are free from material misstatement. Watkins, Hillison, and Morecroft (2004) suggest that audit quality enhances the credibility of financial statements, thereby increasing stakeholder confidence. The Public Company Accounting Oversight Board (PCAOB) (2013) defines audit quality as the probability that an audit will detect and report material misstatements, emphasizing the auditor's role in maintaining the integrity of capital

markets. Knechel et al. (2013) offer a broader view, suggesting that audit quality is influenced by auditor expertise, audit firm size, methodologies, and the regulatory environment.

Manufacturing Sector Output

The manufacturing sector industry played a significant role in the transformation of the economy for example; it is an avenue for increasing productivity related to import replacement and export expansion, creating foreign exchange earning capacity; and raising employment and per capital income which causes unique consumption patterns. Furthermore, Ogwuma (1995) opines that it creates investment capital at a faster rate than any other sector of the economy while promoting wider and more effective linkages among different sectors. Acknowledge this benefit of this sector; the Nigerian government has introduced various strategies to bust the sector such as import substitution strategy, export promotion strategy, the introduction of bank of industry to induced credit facility to the sector and the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS). Loto (2012) revealed that the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) introduced in May 1986 was partly designed to revitalize the manufacturing sector by shifting emphasis to increased domestic sourcing of inputs through monetary and fiscal incentives. The deregulation of the foreign exchange market was also effected to make non-oil exports especially manufacturing sector more competitive even though, this also resulted in massive escalation in input costs. Examining the manufacturing sector over the years in Nigerian economy shows that the share of the manufacturing sector in the gross domestic product has not been impressive. The manufacturing sector contributes 34.94% to gross domestic product in 1986 after the structural adjustment programme. By 1990 and 1995 it decline to 22.84% and 10.17% respectively. The contribution of the Nigerian manufacturing sector to Gross domestic product is very insignificant between 1996 to2012. The year 2000, 2005 and 2012 recorded 6.97%, 2.80% and 1.88% respectively. The insignificant contribution of the sector to gross domestic product is as a results of continues deterioration in infrastructural facility especially the power sector.

Theoretical Framework

The Signaling Theory

Signaling Theory, introduced by Michael Spence in 1973, addresses information asymmetry in markets, where one party in a transaction has more or better information than the other (Spence, 1973). This imbalance can lead to adverse selection and moral hazard, affecting market efficiency. Signaling Theory suggests that one party (the signaler) can convey information to another party (the receiver) through signals, reducing information asymmetry and improving decision-making. In the context of auditing and financial performance, signaling theory is highly relevant. Audits serve as a signal of a company's financial health and integrity to external stakeholders, including investors, creditors, and regulators. High-quality audits provide assurance that the company's financial statements are accurate and reliable, reducing information asymmetry and building trust among stakeholders (Craswell, Francis, & Taylor, 1995). Audit quality is crucial for the signaling process. High-quality audits, characterized by independence, competence, and adherence to professional standards, provide a true and fair view of the company's financial position. For insurance companies, dealing with complex financial transactions and regulatory requirements, audit quality is particularly important (Boolakay & Soobaroyen, 2017). A high-quality audit signals to the market that the company is well-managed and compliant with financial reporting standards, enhancing its credibility and attractiveness to investors (Watts & Zimmerman, 1986). In Nigeria, the insurance sector faces challenges related to financial mismanagement, regulatory non-compliance, and lack of public trust. High-quality audits can address these challenges by providing credible signals about the financial health and governance of insurance companies (Simunic, 1980). The implementation of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) aims to improve transparency and comparability of financial statements. High-quality audits, conducted in accordance with IFRS, signal compliance with international standards, attracting foreign investment and boosting the financial performance of Nigerian insurance companies (Olowookere & Adebisi, 2013).

Empirical Review

Adeniyi, (2025) examined the nexus of audit quality and accounting performance using data from manufacturing firms quoted on the Nigeria Stock Exchange for the period 2012 to 2022. Ex-post facto research design and purposive sampling method was adopted on data sourced from Firms financial statement. Two measures of financial performance; Return on Assets, Net profit margin, and three audit quality variables of audit firm size, audit tenure and audit fees were adopted Hausmann test for selection of model and random-effects panel estimation framework was selected for estimating the relationships and testing hypotheses. The study used Pearson correlation coefficients to examine the required relationships to allow for the non-normality of the variables In this study, the test developed by Levin, Lin and Chu was used to examine the stationarity properties of the variables. This test assumes identical co-integration vectors among the variables. Given that each of the variable in the study is likely to exhibit differences in their emissions, especially as it relates to institutional and outcomes, heterogenous-based results from the Im, Pesaran and Shin and the Augmented Dickey-Fuller tests are carried out in the study. Both the Pedroni and Kao co-integration tests were also carried out. Crosss dependence test and VIF for multicollinearity was conducted on data set. Multiple Regression method was used for the analysis to establish the nature of relationship. Findings confirm a unidirectional causality from Audit firm size, audit tenure and audit fees to Net profit margin while there is unidirectional causality from audit tenure to Returns on Asset. In terms of relationship Audit firm size and audit fees relate with Net profit margin of manufacturing firms significantly while audit tenure does not significantly affect Net profit margin. Audit firm Size, audit fees and audit tenure each has a significant impact on Return on Assets, although the effects of audit fees and audit tenure are positive, while that of audit firm size is negative.

Abdullahi, Norfadzilah, Umar and Ademola, (2020) offers proof on the direct influence of audit quality on the financial performance of listed companies Nigeria. The study employ 84 companies listed on the NSE with 756 samples for the period of nine years which is from 2010 to 2018 based on panel data approach. The research used secondary approach to retrieve data from Thompson Reuters DataStream as well as the financial statement of the listed companies. The results reveal that audit fee shows a positively and insignificant relationship with ROA. This implies that if there is decrease in the amount paid to auditors for audit services, then financial performance of listed companies in Nigeria will increase. Consistent with the agency theory,

auditor size displays a significant positive relationship with ROA. This positive figure implies that a percentage increase in firms audited by Big4, then financial performance (ROA) will also increase. Auditor independence is also seen to be positive and statistically significantly related to the ROA. Finally, auditor independence is found to be more powerful than auditor size on the financial performance. The result of this research will assist the management as well as the executives of the listed companies in Nigeria to put more effort on independence of an auditor.

Otemu, (2020) examined the impact on Auditor pricing of the following; firm size, profitability, Leverage, firm Complexity and Year-end Date. The cross-sectional research design was used for the study with an extensive reliance on secondary data. A sample of 35 manufacturing companies was selected using the simple random sampling technique. Multiple Regression analysis was employed as the method of data analysis. The findings indicate that while profitability, and complexity appeared to be significant determinants of Auditor pricing, Client size, Leverage, and Fiscal year end date were not significant at 5%. Diagnostic analysis conducted indicated that the regression assumptions test such as the Pearson correlation coefficients for collinearity, the Breusch-pagan-Godfrey test for heteroscedasticity, the Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test for higher order autocorrelation and the Ramsey RESET test miss-specification showed that the model satisfies the necessary criterion. The study recommends that that there is the need for regulation of audit fees in the Nigerian environment as the market framework for determining the audit fees may not readily suffice as an advantage for the fostering of auditor dependence

Ugwunta, Ugwuanyi and Ngwa, (2018) examines the effect of audit quality on share prices of Nigerian oil and gas firms using the regression and covariance analyses. Findings from the regression analysis suggests that the composition of the audit committee and auditor type has significant effect on the market prices of quoted firms. There is a positive and significant relationship between audit committee

composition and share prices. The covariance analysis suggests that while auditor type (BIG4/NONBIG4), auditor independence, and composition of the audit committee have a positive and significant relationship with market price of shares, tenure of external auditors has a negative relationship with the market price of shares.

The implication of the findings is that audit quality will enhance reported earnings and hence the share market prices.

Musah (2017) study was to examine the determinant of audit fee with empirical evidence from the Ghana stock exchange. Specifically, the study examined audit fee determinant which included the client size, profitability measured by ROA, LOSS, client risk measured by debt ratio, YEAR (season) and MNC. Using the Simunic (1980) model, this study reveals that client's size of business, international recognition, affiliation of audit firms (Big four firms) and profitability are significant determinants of audit fee in Ghana. Results in study indicate that ignorance of risk factor by the auditors may pose serious threat to fame and reputation of audit firm along with indication of feeble legal regime in Ghana. The results of the study have significant implications for auditors and firms in negotiating audit fees in Ghana. Ohioda and Omokhodu (2018) study examined the firms' characteristics and audit fees in Nigeria. The justification arose from the fact that, auditing profession has come under increased scrutiny over the years about the growing amount of fees paid by audit client and the contributing impact of such fees on auditor independence and the need to investigate the firms' factors that affect audit fees in Nigeria. The study employed a employed time series and cross-session data (panel data) of firms listed at the Nigeria Stock Exchange and data used was gathered from secondary source (annual financial statement) of firms quoted at the Nigeria Stock Exchange from 2013-2017. A sample size of eighty-nine (89) firms was used through the aid of Yaro, (1964) formula for sample size determination. And the statistical tool used in the study was Panel Least Square Regression with the aid of Eview 7.0 and SPSS 20. The study found that, auditor type, client's firm size, client's complexity, client's firm risk and audit committee independence have significant effect on audit fees, while firm's profitability has no effect on audit fees.

Ilaboya, Izevbekhai and Ohiokha, (2017) study aim is to investigate the determinants of abnormal audit fees in Nigerian quoted companies, with specific emphasis on how the firm size, Big4, profitability, joint audit, and leverage impact on abnormal audit fee. The study involved about eighty four (84) manufacturing companies quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange as at 31st December 2014. A sample of 56 companies representing 67% was finally selected for the study. Panel regression estimation technique was used in the analysis of the variables. The choice of the panel regression technique is premised on its quality of unbiasedness, increased data point,

and control for individual heterogeneity. To test the accuracy of the model, they employed the classical regression assumption tests of normality, heteroskedasticity, serial correlation and multi co-linearity. The study found a positive and statistically significant relationship between the interaction of Big 4 audit firms and firm size and the dependent variable of abnormal audit fees.

Fukukava (2018) proposed to investigate whether and to what extent the audit determinants examined in the researches so far influence the audit fees on the Japanese market and examine whether the fees charged by the Japanese audit companies and their cost strategies are significantly different. The study revealed that some determinants, such as: the client's size and complexity, the audit risk, the stock market quotation of the company, the market share of the audit company in that field, and the client's power to negotiate, influence the cost of the audit. Other variables, such as the client's location, the closing date of the financial year and the features of the audit company, influence either only the audit fees, or only the audit cost, or both, but in opposite directions. The author remarks that most of the studies focused on the audit fees, while very little pointed the audit costs from the auditor's perspective.

Gap in Literature

The review pointed out a strong disagreement on the effects of audit quality on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. This disagreement comes in the form of the direction of relationship as well as the level of significance of the relationship. These shortcomings have contributed to the knowledge gap in the literature

Another gap in literature is the coverage of audit quality variables employed in the investigation of effects of audit quality on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The present study includes all the core audit quality variables such as audit fee, audit size and auditor committee to determine the actual effect of effects of audit quality on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher adopted *ex-post facto* design in the study. The study employed secondary data which were sourced from the financial statements of the selected manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Model Specification

The model which will be adopted for this study is the model of Onuorah and Osuji (2014) who examined audit quality and financial performance of listed consumer goods sector in Nigeria

The Model is stated thus:

$$ROA = f(A F, AS, AI)$$

Where:

ROA= Return on Asset

AF= Audit Fee

As= Audit Size

The model is modified by introducing auditor committee

$$ROA = f(A F, AS, AI)$$

The Econometric Equation Form of the Model is:

$$ROA = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AF + \beta_2 AS + \beta_3 AC + \mu$$

Where:

ROA= Return on Asset

AF= Audit Fee

As= Audit Size

AI = Auditor Committee

μ = Stochastic Disturbance (Error Term)

f = Functional Relationship

β_0 = Intercept of Relationship in the Model Constant

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4,$ = are the Coefficients of the Independent Variables

Decision Criteria

The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule is to reject null hypothesis when the computed probability value is less than 0.05 level. Otherwise, accept null hypothesis when the computed probability value greater than 0.05 level.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

	<i>ROA</i>	<i>AF</i>	<i>AS</i>	<i>AC</i>
<i>Mean</i>	0.156175	7.091495	8.406804	7.818365
<i>Maximum</i>	0.236000	15.50000	11.00000	15.00000
<i>Minimum</i>	0.090000	3.000000	6.000000	18.41000
<i>Std. Dev.</i>	0.126025	11.16552	12.45583	15.50235
<i>Jarque-Bera</i>	13.46578	30.11481	18.58473	73.30832
<i>Probability</i>	0.000782	0.000000	0.000092	0.000000
<i>Sum</i>	29.69900	687.8750	844.5600	3474.380
<i>Sum Sq. Dev.</i>	1.524704	11968.22	14894.17	23070.99
<i>Observations</i>	30	30	30	30

Source: Researcher (2024)

The study observed from the descriptive statistics result that the selected manufacturing firms have average financial performance of manufacturing firms of 15.6 percent, maximum and minimum value of

23.6 percent and 9 percent respectively. This reveals that manufacturing firms experience about 15.6 percent growth in return on asset.

Audit Fee has a mean value of 7.09 maximum values 15.50 and minimum values are 3.000 respectively. These values indicate that on the average, audit fee of the manufacturing firms is about 7.1 percent of the operating cost of their firms.

The result also shows average of audit size in manufacturing firms is maintain about 8 members.

The result shows that auditor committee has the average, about 7.81 percent of manufacturing firms.

The Jarque – Bera (JB) which test for normality shows that return on asset audit fee, audit size, auditor committee are normally distributed. The result means that all the explanatory variables are normally distributed, hence no presence of outlier.

Correlation analysis

In examining the relationship among the variables, the study employed the Pearson correlation analysis; the results are presented in table 2.

Table 2. Correlation analysis

	<i>ROA</i>	<i>AF</i>	<i>AS</i>	<i>AC</i>
<i>ROA</i>	1.000000			
<i>AF</i>	-0.211078	1.000000		
<i>AS</i>	-0.282136	-0.145651	1.000000	
<i>AC</i>	0.097123	0.100016	-0.310316	1.000000

Source: Researchers summary (2023) of e-view 8

The findings from the correlation analysis table, shows that financial performance of manufacturing firms has a positive relationship with audit fee, audit size and auditor committee. In checking for multi-co linearity the study noticed that no two explanatory variables were perfectly correlated. This indicates the absence of multi-co linearity problem in the model used for the analysis and also justifies the use of the ordinary least square.

Fixed and Random Effect Test

The summary result of multiple regression analysis is presented below. However, the study takes into cognizance the homogeneity nature of the data, hence the need for testing its effect on the data. The study therefore used Hausman effect test to select between fixed and random effect that is best to be adopted in the study. Below is the summary of the Hausman test result.

Table 3. Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test

Equation: Untitled

Test cross-section random effects

<i>Test Summary</i>	<i>Chi-Sq. Statistic</i>	<i>Chi-Sq. d.f.</i>	<i>Prob.</i>
<i>Cross-section random</i>	5.347202	4	0.1714

Cross-section random effects test comparisons:

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Fixed</i>	<i>Random</i>	<i>Var(Diff.)</i>	<i>Prob.</i>
<i>AF</i>	0.051648	0.045774	0.000011	0.1765
<i>AS</i>	0.150914	0.141147	0.000969	0.7537
<i>AC</i>	0.021635	0.040358	0.000117	0.2831

Source: researcher summary of regression analysis result using E-view 8

The Hausman test result shows a chi-square value of 5.3472 and probability value 0.1714, the chi-square value is greater than 10. Based on the result, the study accept the random effect and reject the fixed effect,

hence we use the random effect to correct the problem of homogeneity in the pool data used for the study. Table 3 below is the summary of the regression result adjusted for fixed effect.

Hypothesis Testing

To evaluate the effect of audit fee on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria and to test our formulated hypotheses, the study used the multiple regression analysis.

Table 4 Regression analysis

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>t-Statistic</i>	<i>Prob.</i>
<i>C</i>	<i>0.388305</i>	<i>0.082929</i>	<i>4.682380</i>	<i>0.0000</i>
<i>AF</i>	<i>0.302746</i>	<i>0.011398</i>	<i>1.964649</i>	<i>0.0525</i>
<i>AS</i>	<i>0.123555</i>	<i>0.001445</i>	<i>2.460367</i>	<i>0.0157</i>
<i>AC</i>	<i>0.000484</i>	<i>0.001232</i>	<i>0.393094</i>	<i>0.6952</i>
<i>R-squared</i>	<i>0.512601</i>	<i>Mean dependent var</i>	<i>0.242614</i>	
<i>Adjusted R-squared</i>	<i>0.463584</i>	<i>S.D. dependent var</i>	<i>0.117222</i>	
<i>S.E. of regression</i>	<i>0.113896</i>	<i>Sum squared resid</i>	<i>1.193453</i>	
<i>F-statistic</i>	<i>2.629639</i>	<i>Durbin-Watson stat</i>	<i>1.868834</i>	
<i>Prob(F-statistic)</i>	<i>0.039328</i>			

Source: Researchers summary of OLS regression Analysis from E-view 8

In table 4 above, the study observed from the model result that the R-sq of 0.5126 and R-sq (adj) 0.4636, respectively. This value indicates that audit quality variable explain about 46.36 percent changes in financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria used in the study. The F-statistics value of 2.6296, and its probability value of 0.0393, shows that the regression model is well specified and the specification is statistically significant at 5% levels. The Durbin Watson value reveals that there is no presence of autocorrelation in our model.

Hypotheses1: Audit fee has no significant effect on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria

The analysis result showed a coefficient value of 0.3027 and a P-value of 0.0525. The coefficient value which reveals the direction and extent of effect that audit fee has on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The result shows a positive value of 0.3027, this reveals that audit fee positively affect the level of financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. This shows that higher audit fee can lead to higher financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria

The probability value of 0.0525 shows that the effect of audit fee on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria is statistically significant. Based on the analysis result, the study accepts the alternate hypothesis it therefore concludes that, audit fee has significant effect on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria

Hypothesis 2: Audit size has no significant effect on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria

The analysis result showed a coefficient value of 0.1236 and a P-value of 0.0157. The coefficient value reveals that audit size positively affect the level of financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. This reveals that higher audit size the better the financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The probability value shows that the effect of audit size on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria is statistically significant. Based on the analysis result, the study accepts the alternate hypothesis it therefore concludes that, audit size has significant effect on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria

Hypothesis 3: Auditor committee has no significant effect on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria

The analysis result showed a coefficient value of 0.00048 and a P-value of 0.6952. The coefficient shows a positive value (though weak), this value reveals that auditor committee can positively influence the level of financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The value indicates that auditor committee

can positively affect the level of financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The probability value shows that the effect of auditor committee though positive on financial performance of manufacturing firms, is not statistically significant. Based on the analysis result, the study rejects the alternate hypothesis and accepts the null hypothesis it therefore concludes that, auditor committee has no significant effect on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria

CONCLUSIONS

This study examined the effect of audit quality on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The result of the study indicate that audit fee, audit size and auditor committee has no significant effect on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria

The study therefore conclude that audit quality has positive and significant effect on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria

RECOMMENDATIONS

Amongst the recommends is that manufacturing firms should adequately pay audit fees that it will not affect performance. Manufacturing firms should improve the audit size below the mean value and that manufacturing firms should not be in a hurry to assign more than one responsibility to each of the auditor committee members since it has significant effect on return on asset.

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